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United Front election of 1954: The Struggle for Democracy

1.ABSTRACT

A significant period in the history of the battle for independence in East Bengal is the election of 1954 and the creation of the United Front. This election served as a "ballot revolution" against the Muslim League leadership's actions against the Bengali people, their language, culture, and history, as well as against the six years of Pakistani authorities' abuse of them. Even after creating the government, the United Front was unable to hold onto power due to the plots and anti-democratic actions of Pakistan's ruling class. Despite this government's failure, the 1954 elections gave political parties a chance to gauge public support. Consequently, this election will have a significant impact on Pakistan's national politics.

Keywords: History, Political Parties, United Front, Comparative Analysis, Strategies, Importance.

2.INTRODUCTION

The election of 1954 is a significant event in the political history of Bengal. In the election of 1954, the political parties of East Bengal in Shere Bangla A.K. Fazlul Haque, Maulana Abdul Hamid Khan Bhasani and Hussain Shaheed Suhrawardy led by forming a 21-point United Front participated in the elections. The United Front won the elections based on the 21-point election manifesto. This election ended nine years of rule and exploitation by the Muslim League and the people of Bengal, through the exercise of their right to vote, raised awareness, which subsequently gave rise to the freedom movement (Ahmed, 1999).

The 1954 Provincial Assembly elections were the first elections of United Pakistan (in East Pakistan). Although elections were supposed to be held in 1951, the government of Pakistan refused to hold elections. They believed that the horrors of the language movement of 1952 would have a major impact on the elections in East Pakistan (Schendel, 2020). Central Muslim League will be defeated in the elections. For this, the ruling Muslim government delayed the election. They wanted their Tabeddar government to be formed in East Bengal. Their rule will remain intact. In 1952, he attacked East Bengal's beloved mother tongue, Bengali, as a strategy. The historic Lahore Resolution of 1940 was accepted in Pakistan. Although Pakistan is supposed to be formed based on this proposal, but subsequently, Pakistan was created on the basis of Mohammad Ali Jinnah's 'binationalism'. East Bengal would have been the first to become an independent state if a 'multiple state' was formed as per the Lahore proposal. But Pakistan was formed as a state based on religious unity on the basis of binationalism since the partition of the country, the people of East Bengal was dreaming of a happy and independent life politically, socially with economic rights (Bose & Sarmila, 2011). But immediately after the creation of Pakistan, the western ruling class started to be protective towards East Bengal. Their activities clearly show that they are completely unwilling to protect the interests of East Pakistan. So they hesitate to give power to the people's representatives through elections (Glynn & Sarah, 2006). But under pressure from East Bengal leaders, the then government of Muhammad Ali announced the election date in March 1954.

Finally, the huge victory of the United Front in the general elections of 1954 is a memorable chapter in the life of the Bengali nation. After winning this election, the people of this country became aware of their rights (Ghatak & Antara, 2022). The results of the elections made Bengalis politically conscious and nationalist in spirit.

3.LITERATURE REVIEW

After 1946 elections were to be held in the provinces in 1951. But the Pakistani ruling group held elections in the provinces of West Pakistan but did not hold elections in East Bengal. This is due to the fear of possible defeat of the Muslim League. Defeats in several by-elections in 1948-49 caused panic among them. Provincial elections were held in East Bengal in 1954. Under the leadership of Sher Bangla AK Fazlul Haque, Maulana Abdul Hamid Khan Bhasani and Hussain Suhrawardy, the United Front was formed on the basis of the 21-point programme (Schendel, 2016). The Awami League, Krishak Praja Party, Nezam Islam and the Democratic Party joined forces to contest the elections against the Muslim League on a 21-point agenda.

3.1 History of the election

Within a few years of Pakistan's founding, political organizations, particularly the East and West Pakistan-based splinter groups of the ruling Muslim League, continued to dispute and fight over regional politics and language, necessitating the creation of new political parties. East Pakistan is the birthplace of regional political organizations including the Awami Muslim League, Krishak-Shramik Party, Communist Party of East Pakistan, Nezam-e-Islami, Pakistan National Congress, etc. Later, the East Pakistani regional political parties and the general populace were forced to come together due to the Muslim League's growing discrimination and oppression in the political, economic, military, and cultural spheres, including the imposition of the Urdu language on the East Pakistanis despite their making up the majority of Pakistan (Gautam, 1998).

In East Pakistan, elections for the Provincial Legislative Assembly were supposed to take place in 1949, but the ruling party kept pushing the date back under various justifications. The government had doubts about the outcome of the Tangail by-elections in 1949 due to the overwhelming participation of candidates from the Muslim League party. As a result, the Legislative Council's 117 open seats had 34 by-elections that were postponed indefinitely (Molla, 1981). The East Pakistan Provincial Council elections were finally set for March 8, 1954 after the government revised the election clause in 1953 (Rahim, 1978).

3.2 Positions of the candidates' parties

In all, 16 parties ran candidates in the 1954 elections for the East Bengal Legislative Assembly. Among the parties running for Muslim seats are the Muslim League, East Pakistan Awami

Muslim League, Krishak Sramik Party, Nezam-e-Islami, Democratic Party, Jubo League, Khilafat Rabbani Party, and Communist Party. On the other hand, the Pakistan National Congress, Scheduled Caste Federation, East Pakistan Samajtantri Dal, Gana Samiti, Abhay Ashram of Comilla, and Minority United States stand out among the parties running for non-Muslim seats (Sarker, 1987). In addition to this, a few political parties that won't be mentioned competed in the elections. Despite 16 parties running for office, the Muslim League and anti-Muslim League won the majority of the votes. A vote was held. The Muslim League was unable to keep its leaders and defectors after the country was divided in 1947. In the 1954 elections, the leaders of the new generation and the defectors stood up against the Muslim League (Majumdar, 2003). While their opponent United Front was a coalition of the right, left, and moderates, the Muslim League was right-wing.

3.3 Political parties election strategies

Different political parties released their election manifestos for the 1954 election, focusing on the goals and dreams of the people of East Bengal.

3.3.1 Plan of the Muslim League

In its electoral platform, the Muslim League pledged to create naval and air force training facilities in East Bengal, make primary education mandatory, and declare Bengali the official state language. The electoral platform includes pledges to develop a governance structure based on the Sunnah of the Qur'an, make religious instruction in mosques mandatory in elementary schools, grant basic rights consistent with Pakistani ideals, and create an Islamic society (Mamun, 1991). Additionally, the manifesto makes promises to address issues with mohajir, minorities, unemployment, public health, agriculture, industry, and jute. The Muslim League's election platform was ambiguous and unclear (Sufia, 2002). Furthermore, even if the Muslim League won the elections and took office, there was no assurance that the election promises would be carried out.

3.3.2 The United Front's founding and mission

In order to give the Muslim League in East Pakistan a harsh lesson in the election, other likeminded parties in the area came together to create an alliance. Awami Muslim League's council meeting in 1953 decided to create a "United Front." Four opposing political parties made up United Front at first. These include the Left Democratic Party, which is led by Haji Danesh, the Awami Muslim League, which is led by Maulana Bhasani, the Nezam-e-Islami,

which is led by Maulana Atahar Ali, and the A. K. Farmer-Labour Party (Haque, 1993). United Front selected a candidate as its electoral symbol. 'Boat'. The key demands of the Awami Muslim League's 42-point election program were included in the United Front's 21-point election platform.

The United Front adopted a 21-point platform on the eve of the elections, placing a high value on the nationalist spirit of Bengal, which was able to appeal to people from all walks of life (Sen, 2009). A key role in its composition was played by Abul Mansoor Ahmad. 21-point plan; Basically, it is:

1. Acceptance of Bengali as a national language of Pakistan
2. Eviction, abolishment, and distribution of surplus land to landless farmers, as well as the elimination of all zamindari and rent-collecting estates.
3. The jute industry was nationalized. Jute fraud while in the Muslim League's cabinet would be identified.
4. The introduction of the cooperative farming system and all other forms of government support for enhancing agriculture growth of handicrafts and small industries.
5. Construction of salt factories. To establish justice by looking into the Salt fraud during the Muslim League government.
6. To set up the rehabilitation of industrial class Mohajers.
7. To create irrigation systems and dig canals to protect the nation from famine and floods.
8. Increasing the nation's industrial and food self-sufficiency. ensuring all worker rights in accordance with ILO norms.
9. The simultaneous introduction of free and required primary education throughout the nation.
10. To only offer instruction in the student's mother tongue. abolish the distinction between public and private schools, and equalize them. converting colleges and universities into government-funded educational establishments.
11. The Dhaka and Rajshahi University Act, among other laws along with the repeal of the Black Law, and the system to transform universities into independent organizations.

12. Lowering the cost of governance. salary adjustments for salaried workers. Salary of the Minister shall not exceed \$1,000.
13. Taking concrete steps to combat corruption, nepotism, and bribery.
14. Revocation of the Public Safety Act and related regulations Prisoners jailed without a trial are released. defending the freedom to assemble and press.
15. Divorce of the judicial branch from the executive branch.
16. Temporarily converting "Burdwan House," the East Bengal Chief Minister's residence, into a dormitory and later into a Bengali language laboratory (now the Bangla Academy).
17. Building of the Shaheed Minar in honor of the 1952 Language Martyrs.
18. Proclamation of the 21st of February as a public holiday.
19. East Bengal was granted complete autonomy in the Lahore Resolution of 1940. The government of East Bengal is in charge of everything, with the exception of foreign relations, national defense, and currency. the relocation of armament production facilities to East Bengal for self-defense.
20. Under no circumstances will the United Front administration extend the Legislative Council's term. six months prior to the Legislative Council's term expiring, the Cabinet resigns, and the Election Commission organizes free and fair elections.
21. A by-election must be held within three months to fill any open seats in the Legislative Council. In the event that the United Front nominee loses three straight by-elections, the Cabinet will resign voluntarily.

3.4 Comparative Analysis of the Muslim League and United Front's Election Programs

The East Bengal attracted population was the main focus of Muslim League and United Front's election campaign. Because of this, it can be seen that there were certain similarities and differences between the commercials of the two parties in the comparative analysis of election advertisements (Shekhar, 2014). The manifestos of the Muslim League and the United Front shared certain commonalities. Problems like those pertaining to the national language, the improvement of the educational system, the resolution of the Mohaj problem, the growth of the jute industry, and agriculture, for instance, may be found in both parties' manifestos, although the issues in the Muslim League manifesto were hazy.

The United Front released a 21-point electoral programme in an effort to appeal to East Bengalis' resentment towards the Muslim League (Matiur, 2016). The United Front's 21-point program was broken down into its individual tenets and presented to Bengalis of all social classes in their election manifesto (Chowdhury, 1994). The people of East Bengal can now comprehend how the United Front will contribute to their future growth.

Almost all sections of the people of East Bengal accepted the 21 points and made the United Front victorious in the elections (Nazneen, 2007). The United Front's election manifesto 21 point was the assurance of ensuring the economic rights of the people through the development of agriculture and industry in East Bengal, as well as the promise of democratic governance, the demand for independence and self-determination of the Bengali nation was embodied in this manifesto.

The advertisement promised pupils in the ninth, tenth, and eleventh grades a popular education in an effort to draw students from East Bengal (Zaheer, 2017). As a result, East Bengal's quest for self-determination was made the key election issue in the United Front's 21-point agenda, which gave special focus to the social, cultural, economic, and political rights of East Bengal.

3.5 Main issues of elections and campaign strategies

The United Front ran campaigns throughout the election that were directed at the feelings of East Bengal's teachers, students, farmers, workers, and general populace (David, 2019). The national language of Bengali and East Bengal's regional autonomy were the Front's top election priorities. The policy of regional discrimination and exploitation, as well as the raising of worker pay, nationalization of the land, and support for cooperatives and small businesses, among other things, were also taken forward. The Muslim League, on the other hand, was unable to raise any general issues (Low, 1997). The establishment of Islamic governance was the only message the Muslim League sent to the electorate. The League has two election slogans. One of them reads, "Islam in peril," and the other, "Pakistan in danger." The electoral campaign of the Muslim League ignored the fundamental issues and requirements of the people of East Bengal. The party was unable to connect with the populace as a result (Feldman, 1988). Additionally, the United Front used the current salt shortage as a weapon against the government. By calling the administration "anti-people," "corrupt," etc., they left it in a very precarious position. The youth and students who supported the Muslim League in the elections of 1946 caused a massive wave in the area; this time, they backed the United Front and campaigned locally to win over the electorate (Chandra, 2009). The likes of Maulana Bhasani,

A. Mansoor Ahmad, Sheikh Mujibur Rahman, Aatur Rahman Khan, and AK Fazlul Haque ran statewide campaigns in East Bengal.

3.6 Election outcomes

Elections were held in East Bengal in 1954 for the first time on the basis of separate elections with seat reservations for certain communities. This was East Bengal's first election with both male and female voters participating freely (Khan, 2012). Only East Bengal residents (male and female) who have reached the age of 21 are eligible to vote in this election. It was especially important that different political parties ran for office.

Voters made up 37.19 percent of the electorate. Poor communication systems, a lack of public knowledge, women's unwillingness to visit the polls, and Muslim women voters in particular had poor turnout due to conservatism, among other factors, all contributed to low turnout (Maitra, 2015). Beginning on March 15, 1954, results of the election held on March 11, 1954, were made public. On April 2, 1954, the complete results were made public (Lawrence, 2018). United Front won 215 of the 237 seats allocated to Muslims, followed by the Muslim League with 9, the Khilafat Rabbani Party with 1, and independents with 12. The fact that the United Front won all nine of the seats designated for women is an important component of the election results. When the 1954 election results were made public, it was discovered that 215 Muslims had been elected directly on the United Front ticket one of these (Shelley, 2009). K. Fazlul Haque was elected from the two Muslim constituencies in Pirojpur West and Pirojpur North East, respectively, and he resigned from the Pirojpur North East seat. As a result, there are currently 214 elected representatives on the United Front ticket.

Eight of the independents who won seats joined the United Front. There were 223 people that were a part of the United Front as a result. On the other hand, the Muslim League would have 10 members if an independent candidate chosen from the Chittagong Muslim Center joined. Out of the 237 Muslim seats in the East Bengal Legislative Assembly in 1954, there were 223 seats for the United Front, 10 seats for the Muslim League, 1 seat for the Khilafat Rabbani Party, and 3 seats for independents (Mushtaq, 2014). The United Front secured an absolute majority in the East Bengal Legislative Assembly based on these election results. On the other hand, the Scheduled Caste Federation (Rasraj Mandal Group) got the greatest number of seats out of the 72 non-Muslim seats. They received 27 seats, with the Pakistan National Congress receiving 24. A noteworthy feature of the election results was that, despite losing many of their

assets, the United Front candidates defeated the chief minister of the Muslim League's provincial cabinet, seven ministers, and important central and provincial Muslim League leaders by a significant margin (Callard, 2010). Among them were prominent figures such as the chief minister Nurul Amin, the minister and top leader Mafizuddin Ahmad, Khan A Sabur, Abdul Hakim Bikrampuri, Iskandar Ali Khan, Abdul Karim, Syed Abdus Salam, Fazlur Rahman, Fakir Abdul Mannan, Monaem Khan.

Bengal provincial election of 1954; Source: studocu.com

However, the existing literature does not provide enough information about the importance of the 1954 election and the contribution of this election in achieving the independence of Bangladesh. At the same time, the reasons behind the victory of the United Front and the defeat of the Muslim League in this election are not clear. On the other hand, despite winning the elections, there was no idea whether the failure of the government was actually responsible for the collapse of the government after only 56 days of formation or the evil plans of the defeated forces. It is also unclear whether these short-term governments were able to achieve their goals.

Therefore, this paper will try to give a clear idea about the election of 1954 as well as provide a fine analysis about the flow of events after the result of this election. For example,

- How important is this election in the politics of Bangladesh, especially the contribution of this election in the 1971 election.

- To find the reasons for success of United Front and failure of Muslim League in elections.
- Post election government formation and its functional role.
- Causes of government collapse and its after effects.

As a result, depending on the preceding literature, this content answer to the following questions:

Research Question 1:

How and to what extent the election of 1954 was able to play a role in the development of Bengali nationality as well as independence movement of Bangladesh?

Research Question 2:

What were the main reasons behind the collapse of the United Front government and to what extent was the failure of the government responsible?

4.METHODOLOGY

This article persecutes a qualitative mode of inquiry where it is done by document analysis, web surfing, books, e-books, prior interviews, various research papers, various journal evaluations, internet forum, web conferencing, online clemency and community, weblog review, YouTube review, online document and case study. This presents both analytical and thematic data. The information that helped to make this paper more valuable has been acknowledged appropriately at the conclusion of the work.

5.LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

This study does not provide enough ideas on the flow of events after the war and has not been able to shed light on the role of this election especially in the politics of Bangladesh. Not even a detailed discussion of how the election had responded in the international arena at that time. Also this paper is done only with the help of secondary data like various books, journals etc. In this case, the information is likely to be somewhat biased.

6.DISCUSSION

6.1 Importance of election

First off, in East Bengal, the 1954 election marked the first free vote to be held under adult

universal suffrage. The ruling Muslim League was unanimously defeated in this election by the

Bengali people. The United Front's electoral triumph provides insight into the standing and acceptance of the local leaders and strengthens the Bengali nation's sense of oneness (Kabir, 2019). The young leader of the United Front, Khaleq Nawaz Khan, defeated numerous powerful members of the ruling party, including Chief Minister Nurul Amin, according to a study of the election results. Syed Abdus Salam, Monayem Khan, Khan E Sabur, Syed Afzal, and Gamir Uddin Pradhan—all ministers of education—were soundly defeated in the referendum. Through the election, it became clear that the United Front's election platform called for the protection of the region's citizens' lives, and that the leaders of the region have a rightful claim to the position of future leader (Schendel, 2016). Furthermore, the Awami Muslim League gained the majority of seats in this election on its own, indicating that the party's leaders have a promising future (Robert, 2007). The election results demonstrate that East Bengal's political, economic, social, and cultural interests are entirely distinct from those of West Pakistan, and that only this region's politicians are capable of defending their interests. After all, the historic Lahore proposition was reflected in the election's results (separate state with South-East region). Following United Front triumph, East Bengal experienced a sense of oneness that had an impact on later national politics (Rounaq, 1998).

Second, these elections and their outcomes sparked a fresh political movement. Politics devoid of religious influence began in 1954 to replace religious dominance in pre-partition politics (Tripathi, 2009). They were conscious that they were deceiving and taking advantage of Bengalis in order to safeguard Islam and Pakistan (Khalek, 2016). The election revealed several instances of Bengalis being exploited and deprived, which ultimately fuelled the caste-based autonomy movement.

Thirdly, politics took on a new dimension as a result of party coalitions formed in East Bengal's best interests (Ahad, 1982). Despite the United Front's participants' differing ideologies, the movement's eventual success was guaranteed by their agreement on the movement's greater goals.

Fourth, the majority of Communists campaigned as United Front candidates rather than party candidates for strategic reasons, and they won 15 seats. In addition, 9 minority candidates from Congress and other parties won as United Front candidates. They were all proposed by the Awami Muslim League. The Awami League went on to become the dominant political force in this nation as a result of the political polarization that followed (Siddiqui, 2005). Following 1954, religious and secular parties took part in all movements, including anti-government

campaigns, separately (Jahan, 2009). In 1955, the Awami Muslim League—the largest party in the United Front—became the Awami League and dropped the word "Muslim" from its name.

Fifth, a change in the nature of national politics in East Bengal is another important outcome of this election. Up until this election, landlords and the upper class in East Bengal shared a single authority ((Lenin, 1997). The influence of well-educated elite groups, including attorneys, journalists, teachers, and businessmen, rose with a university education. Many of the people that were chosen were young (Mahfuzul, 1986). Many of them subsequently made remarkable contributions to Bangladesh's politics during the country's battle of autonomy, independence, and liberation.

Sixth, the election caused Bengalis to lose faith in the Muslim League and other non-Bengali leaders. East Bengalis choose to re-autonomies on the basis of Bengali nationalism. the Muslim League was rejected. The Muslim League never won back the public's favour (Omor, 2017). It consequently turns into a paper party. Following its subsequent division into numerous groups, it lost all of its seats in East Pakistan in the 1970 elections.

6.2 United Front Cabinet formation

Chowdhury Khalikuzzaman the governor of East Bengal, was invited the leader of the United Front parliamentary party Fazlul Haque to form the cabinet following the election. One of the front's commanders, Suhrawardy, was preoccupied with national politics. K. Fazlul Haque created four outstanding cabinets. In addition to serving as Chief Minister, he also oversees the departments of Finance, Home, and Revenue, Justice, Health, and Local Government under Abu Hussain, Civil Supplies and Communications under Ashraf Uddin Ahmad Chowdhury, and Education, Commerce, Labor, and Industries under Syed Azizul Haque (Minhaz, 2017). A full cabinet of 14 people was however established in May.

1954 East Bengal cabinet; Source: commons.m.wikimedia.org

6.3 The reasons for the victory of the United Front and the defeat of the Muslim League

In 1954 elections, the victory of the United Front and the defeat of the Muslim League were some of the main determinants.

6.3.1 Formation of United Front : United Front was a powerful alliance of various political parties of East Bengal irrespective of moderate, leftist, Islamist against the ruling Muslim League which played a major role in the victory.

6.3.2 Program of the United Front: The election manifesto of the United Front reflects the aspirations of all the elites from the elite class of East Bengal to the common peasants and workers, which deeply influenced the people (Sisson, 1999). Promises to make Bengali the national language, provincial autonomy, and price reduction programs created a public response. However The Muslim League developed an image of anti-autonomy and anti-Bengali language. The West Bengal's prominent newspaper Daily Azad stated the reasons of their failure were Non-dealing with the Bengali language, neglect of the economic of Bengal provincial autonomy was attributed to the alienation of the Muslim League leaders from the

general public, lack of concrete economic and political program and strong organization faced the party in a difficult situation (Chatterjee, 1995). In the elections the United Front strongly publicized the various faults of the ruling party. But the Muslim League could not establish any popular issue against the alliance.

6.3.3 Leadership: The three commanders of the victory of the United Front were A. K. Fazlul Haque, Suhrawardy and Maulana Bhasani. Apart from these leaders, young leaders and student leaders were the great strength of the party (Navine, 2016). Students played a role in the team's victory. On the other hand, Muslim League leaders never gained popularity in the region. Most of them were fanatics, separatists, urban elites. At the rural level in 1954, the base of this party was weak (Michael, 2009). The party depended on the chairman and members of the Union Parishad.

6.3.4 Muslim League's failure to frame the system of governance: After attaining independence in just 24 hours, India drew up a constitution and held general elections in 1952. However, in the long 7 years from 1947-54, the ruling Muslim League showed failure in formulating the governance system of Pakistan (Samaddar & Ranabir, 1997). At that time, Pakistan spent 96 crore rupees in the name of auditing the administrative process.

6.3.5 Failure of Muslim League to run the government: Failure of Muslim League to run the government, corruption, nepotism is one of the reasons for their defeat. In 1953 there was famine in Khulna, Barisal. 20 thousand people died in Khulna famine alone. Due to fall in price of jute, farmers are in trouble. Jute costs 19 taka per mane but sells for 3 taka (Richardson, 2015). But the brokers used to sell it for 40-50 taka. Apart from this, salt shortage, unbridled increase in prices of essential commodities including kerosene, oil make people's lives miserable. The law and order situation also deteriorated. In 1947 the total number of crimes increased from 54,566 to 2,18,670 in 1950 (Yongle, 2016). The defeat of Chief Minister Nurul Amin itself proves the party's bankruptcy.

6.3.6 Muslim League Infighting: After the creation of Pakistan in 1947, internal conflicts arose between the ruling Muslim League in various provinces. Within 1950, the Muslim League broke up in East Pakistan Awami Muslim League, Jinnah Muslim League, Awami Muslim League, Jinnah Awami Muslim League was formed. Progressive and renegade leaders left the Muslim League (Gupta & Jyoti, 1981). The formation of new opposition parties weakened the Muslim League. Many, leaders and Karmas participated in Shamsul Haque's

election campaign and voted for him in the Tangail by-election of 1949, excluding his party's nominee.

6.3.7 Extreme Repressive Policy of Muslim League: Muslim League unites government and state. Sardar Abdur Rab Nishtar, Jandarel leader of the Muslim League, said, "The Muslim League is now subservient to the government" (Keshab, 2009). Declaring any form of criticism of the government as treason, harassing and arresting dissident political leaders and activists. As a result people are angry with the party.

6.3.8 Endless discrimination between East-West Pakistan: The people of East Bengal suffer from discrimination in all areas including socio-social, educational, military, political. By highlighting these in their programme, the United Front was able to create a reaction against the Muslim League in the public mind (Basu, 2006). They demanded self-rule not under nonBengalis leadership but through provincial autonomy. However, the issue of autonomy is completely avoided by the Muslim League in their program.

6.3.9 Unlimited Corruption and Nepotism: The Muslim League government started corruption and nepotism, unrestrained looting in various ways all over the country with the connivance of high officials (Murshid, 2009). The pent-up discontent of the common people began to accumulate, which manifested itself in a landslide in the elections.

6.3.10 Reasons for defeat according to Muslim League mouthpiece Dainik Azad: Muslim League mouthpiece Dainik Azad mentions 10 specific reasons for Muslim League's defeat and United Front's success.

- Injustice to Muslim League's demand for Bengali language, Nurul Amin government's suppression policy regarding language movement;
- Central policy towards East Bengal, lack of tolerance, injustice and exploitation policy;
- Proposal and attitude not to give autonomy to East Bengal based on Lahore proposal;
- Financial plight of the people of East Bengal;
- Delay in constitution making;
- Muslim League's lack of mass communication;
- Integration of Muslim League and Ministry;
- Lack of Muslim League staff and hostile attitude of students and youth towards Muslim League;
- Lack of personality leadership within the Muslim League and
- Government failure to fight corruption.

6.4 Central intervention and United Front cabinet abolished

From the very beginning of the formation of the United Front cabinet, there was great dissatisfaction among the coalition parties over the ministership, which was the extreme weakness of the United Front government. A few days after the formation of the cabinet, Chief Minister Fazlul Huq visited Kolkata and gave an emotional speech about the people of the two Bengals and their language, literature, and culture, which the ruling Makes the government angry (Klein, 2013). After forming the United Front government, as per the election promise, February 21 was a public holiday and declared 'Burdwan House', the official residence of the Chief Minister of the previous Muslim League government, as a memorial laboratory of the language movement, causing displeasure with the central government (Khan, 2008). At this time, two incidents left the Haque cabinet in a state of extreme embarrassment. They are the bloody clashes between the prison authorities and local Mohalla residents in front of the Dhaka Central Jail on May 2 and the bloody clashes between Bengali and Bihari workers at Adamji Patak on May 15, which the central government termed as the weakness of the United Front government (Siegfried, 2016). Finally, Fazlul Haque's so-called interview with New York Times' correspondent Callahan upset the central government. According to the information published in the newspaper, Fazlul Haque expressed his desire to declare the independence of East Bengal. Chief Minister Fazlul Haque failed to convince the central government in this regard despite various efforts (Islam, 2018). The Central Government called the United Front under Section 92(a) of the Government of India Act of 30 May 1954. Dismissed the cabinet and declared Governor's rule in East Bengal. Thus the United Front Cabinet came to an end after only 56 days.

6.5 Dismissal of United Front Cabinet and reaction in East Bengal

The Pakistani government started mass arrests of United Front activists. Former Chief Minister Fazlul Haque was placed under house arrest, Maulana Bhasani was banned from entering the country, many young leaders including Sheikh Mujib were arrested and United Front offices were locked. In response to this there was great discontent in East Bengal and the Front workers, failing to hold a meeting in the office, convened a meeting at the residence of Front leader Abu Hussain Sarkar (Henry, 2014). In the meeting, the leaders avoided the decision to cancel the cabinet and build a strong movement against the government's mass arrests to go to

the villages and undertake revolutionary and destructive activities. However, there was no result. On the one hand, the reluctance of Fazlul Haque and the absence of Bhasani and Suhrawardy, on the other hand, the movement of the United Front ended in failure (Milan, 1998).

6.6 Importance of 1954 election and formation of United Front government

For the first time in the political history of Bengal and Pakistan, in the 1954 election, the political parties entered into an election war against each other by presenting a specific election manifesto (Iqbal, 2018). Among the two main political parties participating in the elections, the Muslim League prioritized the protection of 'Islam' and 'Pakistan' in its election manifesto, but the United Front announced a 21-point program containing demands for the welfare of the people of East Bengal and the establishment of autonomy (Batabyal, 2020). The 21-point program of the United Front later served as a milestone in the preparation and campaigning of the election manifesto in the 1970 elections, along with the 6-point program of the Bengali independence movement, the 6-point program of the Awami League, and the 11-point program of the struggling student society. After the presentation of the election manifesto of the political parties in the 1954 elections, there was a great reaction among the people of East Bengal. The reaction of the people of East Bengal was reflected in the victory of the United Front by voting against the Muslim League in the elections (Linton & Suzannah, 2010). The victory of the United Front had a far-reaching influence on the politics of East Bengal and Pakistan. The victory of the United Front proves that the people of East Bengal are fully united on the question of full regional autonomy and are determined to maintain their linguistic and cultural identity. Not only this, it is also clear that not the Muslim League but the United Front has the right to represent East Bengal (Hosseini, 1987). As a result, Bengali leadership was established instead of the leadership of non-Bengali Khwaja families and businessmen and elites.

But the movement in East Bengal against the introduction of undemocratic process by ignoring the verdict of 1954 election did not stop. The first constitution of Pakistan was drafted in 1956, in which East Bengal played a significant role (Norman, 2019). Behind the writing of the constitution. K. Fazlul Haque, Hossain Shaheed Suhrawardy, Abul Mansoor Ahmad, Ataur Rahman Khan and Sheikh Mujibur Rahman had important roles. Autonomy movement, Sheikh Mujib's speech on March 7, 1971 repeatedly referred to the injustice and hostile policies of the United Front.

Although the United Front Cabinet was an apparent failure, its impact was far-reaching. Although the Center was able to abolish the cabinet and suppress the anti-government movement for the time being with its autocratic power, the spirit and sense of unity among the Bengali nation through the elections (Bellin, 2016). It could not stop what had developed. It was evident through the active participation of Bengalis in the anti-central government movement in the sixties. The Muslim League was so rejected by the people of East Bengal in this election that it was never again possible for the Muslim League to gain public support (Park, 2014). Later, this election had a far-reaching impact on the national politics of Pakistan. Apart from the spirit of progressiveness in the minds of Bengalis, this election played a far-reaching role in the independence movement and the development of independent Bangladesh.

7. CONCLUSION

The victory of the United Front in the 1954 elections was of immense importance. This victory ended the Muslim League's long seven-year rule of exploitation and oppression. The 1954 election was a united protest against the unjust, discriminatory failed rule of the Muslim League. The Bengali nation through this election made the Muslim League understand that they no longer want the Muslim League in East Bengal.

Awami Muslim League's maximum number of seats among the United Front political parties indicates their strong leadership in East Bengal in the future. Secular ideas were created in the politics of East Bengal through this election. After all, through this election, the Muslim League has created a lot of distrust in the minds of Bengalis towards the non-Bengali leadership. They understand that the true liberation of Bengalis is not possible by the West Pakistanis and their domestic allies. As a result, the people of East Bengal expressed their full support for autonomy on the basis of Bengali nationalist ideals.

8. REFERENCE

- Ahamed, Emajuddin, and D. R. J. A. Nazneen. "Islam in Bangladesh: Revivalism or power politics?." *Asian Survey* (1990): 795-808.
- Akmam, Wardatul. "Atrocities against humanity during the liberation war in Bangladesh: A case of genocide." *Journal of Genocide Research* 4, no. 4 (2002): 543-559.
- Al Mostofa, Mr Mamun, and Saleh Ahmed. "Assignment on: Twenty-one point of the United Front: Its Political Economy And Class Basis."
- Batabyal, Guru Saday. *Politico-military Strategy of the Bangladesh Liberation War, 1971*. Routledge India, 2020.
- Bose, Sarmila. "The question of genocide and the quest for justice in the 1971 war." *Journal of Genocide Research* 13, no. 4 (2011): 393-419.
- Callard, Keith B. *Pakistan, a political study*. Macmillan, 1957.
- Debnath, Angela. "The Bangladesh genocide: The plight of women 1." In *Plight and fate of women during and following genocide*, pp. 47-66. Routledge, 2017.
- Deb, Steffi S. "The Liberation War of Bangladesh: Women and the Alternative Narratives of the War." *Journal of International Women's Studies* 22, no. 4 (2021): 78-86.
- Dowlah, Caf. *The Bangladesh Liberation War, the Sheikh Mujib Regime, and Contemporary Controversies*. Lexington Books, 2016.
- Ghatak, Antara. "Negotiating gender and disability in the Bangladesh Liberation War, 1971." *The Routledge Companion to Gender, Sexuality and Culture* (2022).
- Gill, John H. *An atlas of the 1971 India-Pakistan War: the creation of Bangladesh*. National Defense University, Near East South Asia Center for Strategic Studies, 2003.
- Glynn, Sarah. "The Spirit of '71: how the Bangladeshi War of Independence has haunted Tower Hamlets." (2006).
- Gupta, Jyoti Sen. *Bangladesh, in Blood and Tears*. Calcutta: Naya Prokash, 1981.

Iqbal, Mohammad Zubair, and Shabir Hussain. "Indo-Pak wars (1948, 1965, 1971,1999): Projecting the Nationalistic Narrative." *Journal of Political Studies* 25, no. 1 (2018).

Khan, Akbar Ali. *Discovery of Bangladesh: Explorations into dynamics of a hidden nation*. University Press Limited, 1996.

Linton, Suzannah. "Completing the circle: Accountability for the crimes of the 1971 Bangladesh war of liberation." In *Completing The Circle: Accountability for the Crimes of the 1971 Bangladesh War of Liberation*", *Criminal Law Forum*, vol. 21, no. 2, pp. 191-311. 2010.

Mohaiemen, Naeem. "Flying blind: waiting for a real reckoning on 1971." *Economicand Political weekly* (2011): 40-52.

Murshid, Navine. "The Genocide of 1971 and the Politics of Justice." In *Routledge handbook of contemporary Bangladesh*, pp. 52-61. Routledge, 2016.

Ouassini, Anwar, and Nabil Ouassini. "3 "Kill 3 Million and the Rest Will Eat of Our Hands": Genocide, Rape, and the Bangladeshi War of Liberation." *Genocide and Mass Violence in Asia* 118, no. 1 (1996): 40.

Rahaman, Arifur, AKM Jamal Uddin, and Md Shakhawat Hossain. "Origin and sociocultural formation of Bihari identity: A study on Bihari community in Bangladesh." *International Journal of Social, Political and Economic Research* 7, no. 4 (2020): 879903.

Ranjan, Amit. "Bangladesh liberation war of 1971: Narratives, impacts and the actors." *India Quarterly* 72, no. 2 (2016): 132-145.

Ray, Sally. "Political leadership in Bangla Desh." *Quadrant* 16, no. 1 (1972): 14-20.

Riaz, Ali, and C. Christine Fair, eds. *Political Islam and governance in Bangladesh*. London: Routledge, 2011.

Saikia, Yasmin. "Beyond the archive of silence: Narratives of violence of the 1971 liberation war of Bangladesh." In *History Workshop Journal*, vol. 58, no. 1, pp. 275287. Oxford University Press, 2004.

Saikia, Yasmin. "Women, war, and the making of Bangladesh." In *Women, War, and the Making of Bangladesh*. Duke University Press, 2011.

Samaddar, Ranabir. "Interpretations of the Bangladesh War." *India International Centre Quarterly* 24, no. 2/3 (1997): 219-227.

Tripathi, Salil. *The colonel who would not repent: The Bangladesh war and its unquiet legacy*. Yale University Press, 2016.

Van Schendel, Willem. "A war within a war: Mizo rebels and the Bangladesh liberation struggle." *Modern Asian Studies* 50, no. 1 (2016): 75-117.

Van Schendel, Willem. *A history of Bangladesh*. Cambridge University Press, 2020.

Wolf, Siegfried O. "The international context of Bangladesh liberation war." *The Independent*, March 29 (2013): 14-14.